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Treatment of Periodontal Diseases in Leukemia

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Abstract: *Periodontal diseases, as well as dental caries, are very common. According to WHO, about 95% of the world's adult population and 80% of children have some symptoms of periodontal disease. What is periodontitis?*

Periodontal disease, as well as dental caries, is very common. According to the WHO, approximately 95% of the world's adult population and 80% of children have some symptoms of periodontal disease.

What is periodontitis? The periodontium is a complex of tissues that surround the tooth and provide its fixation in the jaw bones. This complex includes the gums, the periodontal ligament connecting the tooth root with the bone socket, the bone tissue of the alveolar processes and the cementum of the tooth root. In various periodontal diseases, any part of the periodontal complex or the entire periodontal can be involved in the pathological process. The nature of the pathological process also varies: dystrophic, inflammatory or tumoral.

Key words: *Diseases of the oral cavity; Reasons; Types; Symptoms; Diagnostics; Treatment.*

Introduction:

90-95% of all periodontal diseases are inflammatory, such as gingivitis and periodontitis. Therefore, we will dwell on them in more detail.

Gingivitis is an inflammatory process in the tissues at the edge of the gums, in which only the superficial tissues of the gums are affected.

Periodontitis is an inflammatory process involving all periodontal structures. It is characterized by destruction of the periodontal ligament and progressive destruction of the alveolar processes of the jaw bones.

In fact, gingivitis and periodontitis are two interrelated forms of the disease, since the inflammatory process occurs primarily in the gum tissues and gradually involves the main structures of periodontitis: the gingival ligament and alveolar bones.

Currently, the main local pathogenetic factors of inflammatory periodontal diseases have been identified. These are the accumulation of dental plaque (microbial factor), disruption of the structure of the oral vestibule, dental anomalies, and supracontacts.

The inflammatory process in the gum tissue is initially caused by a large accumulation of microbes and the enzymes and toxins they secrete. When the inflammation is limited to the gums and the underlying tissues are not affected, we are dealing with gingivitis, which occurs with periods of exacerbation and remission with varying degrees of activity in different patients.

Research methods and materials: The difference in the nature of the course of gingivitis is determined by the state of the general defense mechanisms in patients. Therefore, with the absolute recognition of the microbial factor, the "interest" of the whole organism in the development and course of this purely local process is never in doubt.

Bleeding gums during brushing are noted by almost all patients with gingivitis. Complaints of pain and bleeding gums during meals may also be present. The general condition, with rare exceptions, is not impaired.

When examining patients, a large amount of soft dental plaque is usually detected, especially on the necks of the teeth. The gingival margin is usually hyperemic, swollen, and the gums bleed easily on probing.

Since gingivitis only inflames superficial tissues, which are easy to examine and target therapeutic interventions, the treatment of this disease is very effective.

The main method of treating and preventing gingivitis is to remove microbial accumulations, that is, hygiene measures.

Hygiene products - toothpastes and toothbrushes - are the main weapons against inflammatory periodontal diseases. Moreover, they are equally effective in both periodontal inflammation and caries, since in both cases the microbial factor is the main one.

However, despite the availability of such an effective and inexpensive preventive and therapeutic tool, the problem of inflammatory periodontal diseases remains very relevant. Already in childhood, in 30-80% of cases, the initial stage of the disease is diagnosed in the form of superficial inflammation - gingivitis, the course of which is characterized by alternating periods of intense inflammatory reaction and a relatively favorable state of the periodontium. With age, the intensity and prevalence of the inflammatory reaction in the periodontium increases: in adolescents with gingivitis, destructive changes in periodontitis are observed in 2-6% of cases. Later, the frequency of superficial inflammatory changes, manifested as gingivitis, decreases, and the prevalence of deeper destructive phenomena in periodontitis of varying severity increases significantly.

The problem of adequate oral hygiene and the formation of the necessary hygiene skills in children is very complex. Today, the domestic market offers very high-quality hygiene products (pastes and brushes). The question is different: to achieve the necessary cleaning of teeth and gums, one surface of

the tooth should be brushed at least 20 times, the total time for cleaning the teeth - from the outside and inside - should be at least three minutes, otherwise microbial plaque will remain. In addition, the spaces between the teeth should be treated with floss (dental floss). In order to form in children the need to brush their teeth at least twice a day, they should be accustomed to this from a very early age.

Unless the child is consistently encouraged to take care of his or her teeth, it is difficult to expect significant results in terms of the condition of the gums and teeth. It should be remembered that the quality of brushing teeth largely depends on individual manual dexterity. Many children, no matter how hard they try, cannot brush their teeth well. The above directly applies to children with general developmental disabilities.

The doctor should regularly carry out appropriate treatment or prescribe drugs that effectively suppress the activity of microorganisms and slow down the formation of microbial clusters. The most effective drug for these purposes today is chlorhexidine bigluconate, which sharply inhibits the activity of all microbial clusters that damage periodontal tissues and hard dental tissues. In addition, it actively suppresses herpes viruses, fungi and has a weak analgesic effect. The disadvantage of this remedy is its persistent bitter taste, which limits the use of this drug, especially in children. The drug "Corsodyl", which has recently appeared on our market, is devoid of this drawback. Therefore, it is widely used in many countries of the world. Staining of the tongue and surfaces of fillings is a property of chlorhexidine - a temporary phenomenon that passes very quickly. At the same time, the effect of using chlorhexidine as a therapeutic and prophylactic measure is very high and stable. Patients apply the drug themselves, the course of treatment is 5-7 days.

As soon as the inflammation overcomes the main barrier - the periodontal ligament, it passes to the underlying tissues - the periodontium and alveolar bone. Being a logical continuation of gingivitis, this form acquires completely new features. Firstly, a periodontal pocket is formed, in which the accumulation of microbes is reliably hidden and is not removed during tooth brushing. Secondly, in the depths of the periodontal pockets, the most aggressive types of microbes - anaerobes, spirochetes - actively multiply, their ability to cause damage is very high. Thirdly, both the microorganisms themselves and their enzymes and toxins from the pockets easily penetrate into the underlying structures, dissolving them. As a result, the stability of the teeth decreases, they become mobile, and the mechanical load on the teeth during chewing is damaged. As a result of this damage, the destruction of the supporting apparatus of the tooth occurs especially quickly, which, in turn, contributes to the further spread of microbial accumulations. Periodontitis develops.

Patients' complaints are usually tooth mobility, bleeding gums, bad breath, fan-shaped divergence of the upper front teeth, and exposed necks of the teeth.

Examination reveals hyperemia of the gingival margin, often with a cyanotic color, with the gums not fitting tightly to the necks of the teeth;

Results: During probing, periodontal pockets of varying depths are detected, depending on the severity of the process. Supra- and subgingival tooth deposits are present. In the case of a pronounced process, purulent discharge from the periodontal pockets and significant tooth mobility may occur. Radiographically, periodontitis shows a decrease in the height of the alveolar process due to resorption of the bone tissue of the interalveolar septa.

Treatment of periodontitis is primarily aimed at removing microbial accumulations, tartar and granulations from periodontal pockets. If periodontal pockets are very deep, their complete treatment is possible only by surgery. And after surgery, the main task is to prevent further penetration of

microbial masses. This is more difficult to achieve, but in this case, the main method of prevention is high-quality controlled oral hygiene, the use of effective antimicrobial rinses, among which Corsodyl is recognized as the most effective today.

There are several forms of inflammatory periodontal disease, characterized by increasing aggressiveness. Their main difference is the presence of specific microorganisms and their combinations.

The process occurs in childhood and involves permanent and even baby teeth. Early development and aggressive course are associated with the presence of defects in general defenses - monocytes and polymorphonuclear leukocytes in such patients. In such cases, the tactics of specialists are to conduct a more thorough fight against microbes. But the result can only be achieved through the efforts of general practitioners - if it is possible to eliminate blood cell defects using targeted drugs.

Focal juvenile periodontitis. With this form of periodontitis, selective damage to the supporting apparatus of the first permanent teeth occurs. The disease is caused by the species *Actinobacillus Actinomycetes comitans*. In most cases, it occurs in children whose parents are carriers of the microorganism. The process occurs with a minimal inflammatory reaction. Its rapid spread is due to the fact that this type of microorganisms has the ability to suppress leukocyte chemotaxis and do not have time to produce antibodies under such conditions. Therefore, subsequent permanent teeth are rarely damaged, since specific antibodies have time to form and exert their protective effect later. Treatment involves active antibiotic therapy - at least 3 weeks - in combination with local interventions. The duration and necessity of general antibiotic therapy are due to the fact that microorganisms live not only in the periodontal groove and subsequently in the periodontal pocket, but also penetrate deep into the tissues and bone structures, where they are stably maintained.

Rapidly developing periodontitis, as well as periodontitis resistant to medical interventions, is caused by a specific microflora: *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (formerly *bacterioides*), *Actinobacillus Actinomycetes comitans* and *Prevotella intermedia*. Moreover, their combination usually occurs. In this case, the indicated microorganisms have a sharply positive synergistic interaction, and the microbial composition not only has a sharply destructive effect on the tissues, but also suppresses the action of protective cells. In addition, the deep penetration of these microorganisms into the tissues is characteristic.

Discussion: Medical tactics consist of careful mechanical treatment of periodontal pockets and intensive antimicrobial therapy. Local oral administration of metronidazole or tetracycline is effective. It is recommended to perform flap operations no later than 3-4 weeks after the start of antimicrobial therapy, otherwise - if the listed microorganisms remain viable - surgical treatment will be ineffective. Corsodyl has a good effect after surgical treatment. Given the relatively local activity, the most reliable criterion for the effectiveness of treatment is microbiological analysis of the contents of periodontal pockets and tissue biopsies. It follows from this that in a number of cases the treatment of such patients should be carried out only in specialized institutions with the necessary conditions. And, of course, no treatment can be effective, especially when it comes to the long-term prognosis, if there is no proper care of the oral cavity.

One of the diseases based on the dystrophic process is periodontitis. Periodontitis is an atrophic-dystrophic process in the periodontal tissues. This disease has very few symptoms. What brings patients to the doctor?

This is mainly a cosmetic defect, manifested in the exposure of the roots of the teeth and the increase in their clinical crown. Patients complain that "the gums are receding and the teeth are becoming longer", which is especially annoying in the frontal area. In some cases, patients are bothered by itching in the gums, as well as pain from the exposed necks of the teeth.

The most common observation during the examination is the uniformity of atrophic manifestations in the area of all teeth and the direct involvement of dental tissues in the process - this is manifested in the presence of wedge-shaped defects. This pathology is characterized by slow development and relative asymptomaticity.

The cause of this pathology is not clear, it is considered either an early development of involutonal processes or a manifestation of general disorders in periodontitis, that is, a syndrome or symptom of general disorders. However, very clear and clearly expressed clinical signs allow us to distinguish this form of the disease.

There is no adequate treatment for periodontal disease, since the cause of the disease has not been identified. The doctor carries out only symptomatic treatment - eliminates hypersensitivity of the teeth, prescribes massage or auto-massage of the gums to correct trophic disorders, and also performs filling of wedge-shaped defects. To satisfy the wishes of patients, some surgeons perform vestibuloplastic operations. However, this should not be done, since the effect of such interventions is very short-lived.

Conclusion: What is actually effective is the use of products that eliminate the pain sensitivity of the exposed cheeks of the teeth. For this purpose, fluoride varnish, fluogel and baking soda powder are used. Currently, there is a sensodyne paste on the market that successfully relieves tooth sensitivity, and the patient can use it independently. The doctor should warn patients with this disease not to use hard brushes or make horizontal movements so as not to increase the depth of the wedge-shaped defects.

Tumors and tumor-like lesions are also among the diseases that are difficult to predict, since they develop only in people who are predisposed to this process. The impetus for the onset of the development of the process can be hormonal changes, in particular, the accumulation of somatotrophic hormone during puberty or pregnancy, the presence of a chronic traumatic factor or previous inflammation. However, all these are only additional risk factors that cause the development of such lesions in people predisposed to this process.

Treatment and preventive measures consist in eliminating trauma, inflammation and, if necessary, surgical removal of overgrown tissues (gingival fibromatosis, hypertrophic gingivitis, epulis, interradicular granuloma). Currently, another serious factor has emerged that contributes to the development of this type of pathology: the use of anabolic steroids by young people involved in bodybuilding and professional strength sports. The doctor's options here are simple: explanation and advice.

What leads to a positive result in such cases? Maximum thorough oral hygiene, the use of effective antiseptic and antibacterial rinses by the patients themselves after an active course of treatment.

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